

Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate and Students' Intention to Engage in Cultural Events: A Parallel Multiple Mediation Analysis of Attitude to Multiculturalism at School and Cultural Competence as Groundwork for Culture and the Arts Confluence Program

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Abstract:

Youth participation matters in nurturing culture and heritage. However, there has been a dearth of research conducted to comprehensively examine youth participation and frame it in the context of cultural heritage and education. This study examined the mediating role of attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence on the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events as a basis to devise an institutional culture-based activity. Using 705 student samples of Holy Cross of Davao College selected via quota sampling, it was revealed that attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence significantly and fully mediated the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events affirming the social cognitive theory. These findings lead to a relevant groundwork for culture and the arts confluence program that emphasizes enhancing students' cultural competence

and their attitude towards multiculturalism while also focusing on strengthening teachers' strategies to establish a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational environment. Further work in this area can enhance one's understanding of cultural competence and multicultural attitudes and inform future cultural education programs.

Keywords: *Classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude towards multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, intention to engage in cultural events, culture and the arts.*

Introduction

The present generation is facing a redoubtable problem: the decline in knowledge and interest in local culture, a problem worsened by the rapid influence and romanticization of foreign cultures over their own (Rosa et al., 2021). Despite various efforts to increase engagement, young people's participation in culture and the arts remains consistently declining (Briška & Siliņa-Jasjukeviča, 2020). Various studies have revealed that young individuals show less interest in local culture (Mancacaritadipura, 2007, as cited by Mekonnen et al., 2022) and are disengaged from cultural activities (Polvonova, 2024). In Indonesia, this disinterest has decreased local cultural knowledge among youth (Shomiyatun, 2019; Darmansa et al., 2019; Houtman, 2017; Priatna, 2017). Similarly, ethnographic research conducted in Western Slovenia revealed a lack of interest in heritage practices among the young population (Bajec, 2019). This disinterest in cultural participation is often due to initial limitations transforming into a broader unwillingness to engage (Kacane, 2021).

The Philippines is scuffling with the same challenges in preserving its cultural heritage due to globalization, modernization, language shifts, lack of institutional support, generational gaps, and lack of awareness (Besmonte, 2022; Lobo, 2023; Pacio, 2023). Villa (2023) stated that influences from different generations and other countries erode Filipino cultural heritage. Her study further revealed that this issue is evident in the low cultural awareness among senior high school students at Tukuran Technical Vocational School. She further stated that Filipino cultural heritage continues to fade despite various culture-based activities. Even indigenous students, it was revealed that they are already less engaged in different activities in school (Cuizon & Garcia, 2013). Moreover, the Center of Culture and the Arts hosted a cultural symposium program last year, extending an invitation to all college students from various programs; however, despite the open invitation, the attendance turnout revealed that only a few

students showed interest and participated in the event.

The collected evidence emphasizing cultural crisis in contemporary times led the researchers to conduct this research from an educational perspective involving the younger generation, the college students. This is crucial because youth participation is essential for culture and heritage conservation (UNESCO, 2002). This study aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4, Target 4.7, which emphasizes the need for learners to gain knowledge and skills that promote sustainable development and cultural diversity appreciation (Carlsen & Bruggemann, 2022; United Nations, 2015). Cultural activities provide entertainment and foster creative and experiential learning, aiding in self-discovery and mental health development (Storey, 2010, as cited by Longinou, 2020). Belongingness, influenced by social identities and campus conditions, is critical for college success (Strayhorn, 2018), and hosting events that celebrate global cultural diversity enhances students' intercultural sensitivity (Klak & Martin, 2003). Furthermore, young people are the future guardians of their culture and heritage (UNESCO, 2021). Thus, educational institutions must emphasize Filipino intangible culture and promote cultural heritage awareness (Pastera, 2024; Mike & David, 2006, as cited by Mekonnen et al., 2022), as understanding cultural issues is vital in today's education (Briška & Siliņa-Jasjukeviča, 2020).

On the other hand, this study is grounded on Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory, which proposes that human behavior is the product of the interaction between personal factors, environmental influences, and behavioral patterns (Bandura, 1986). This theoretical framework supports the idea that the environment (cultural diversity climate) influences internal or personal factors (attitudes and competence), which in turn affect behavioral intentions (engagement in cultural events). Putting the perspective into this study, the researchers value a positive classroom cultural diversity climate fostering favorable

attitudes toward multiculturalism and enhancing cultural competence. These attitudes and competencies mediate the relationship between

the perceived diversity climate and college students' intention to engage in cultural events.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Objectives

This study aimed to examine the mediating effects of attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence on the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events among Holy Cross of Davao College students. Ultimately, from the findings obtained, this study intends to devise an institutional culture-based activity tailored to the needs of the students. Specifically, these are the study's objectives:

1. To ascertain the levels of classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, and intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students.
2. To determine the strength and significance of the bivariate correlations among classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, and intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students.

3. To determine whether attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence mediates the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students.

4. To devise a culture-based activity for the Holy Cross of Davao College students that will be implemented by the Center for Culture and the Arts.

Below are the null hypotheses of the study:

H_{01} . There are no significant positive correlations manifest among Holy Cross of Davao College students' perceived classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, and intention to engage in cultural events.

H_{02} . The attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence does not mediate the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students.

Materials and Methods

This study is a quantitative, nonexperimental investigation utilizing a causal research design. The research was conducted at Holy Cross of Davao College, a private Catholic higher education institution located at Sta. Ana Avenue Corner C. De Guzman Street, Barangay 14-B, Davao City, Philippines. This institution was selected due to its established Center for Culture and the Arts, which aims to understand the factors influencing college students' intentions to engage in cultural events. The study also sought to determine the necessity of continuing last year's cultural symposium and identify other aspects to enhance and further intensify students' cultural awareness, competence, and appreciation.

The respondents ($n = 705$) were college students, who are males, females, and members of the LGBTQ+ community, aged 18 and above, and enrolled in various programs at Holy Cross of Davao College during the academic year 2023-2024. All respondents were provided with voluntary consent to join the study. The majority of respondents were from the School of Business and Management Education ($n = 160$, 23%), followed by the School of Teacher Education ($n = 128$, 18%), College of Hospitality and Tourism Management Education ($n = 121$, 17%), College of Maritime Education ($n = 102$, 14%), College of Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication ($n = 84$, 12%), College of Engineering and Technology ($n = 58$, 8%), and College of Criminal Justice Education ($n = 52$, 7%).

The study utilized adapted scales validated by three experts in the field of social studies. The scales were modified to ensure they were relevant and appropriate to the context of the target respondents and the higher education institution in which they enrolled. The revised survey questionnaire was pilot-tested, and the responses were gauged on a four-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = strongly agree). The overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the revised survey questionnaire was 0.901, indicating high reliability.

The scales used in this study included:

1. Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate Scale (CCDCS) developed by Schachner et al. (2021), this scale has six domains with 31 items: contact and cooperation (three items), equal treatment (five items), color inclusivity (five items), heritage, culture, and intercultural learning (seven items), critical consciousness (five items), and polyculturalism (six items). The Cronbach's alpha for CCDCS was 0.886.
2. Cultural Competence Scale (CCS) developed by Domenech Rodriguez et al. (2022), it includes four domains with thirty-six items: knowledge (twelve items), awareness of others (ten items), proactive skills development (seven items), and awareness of self (seven items). The Cronbach's alpha for CCS was 0.850.
3. Attitude to Multiculturality at School Scale (AMSS) was developed by Lemp et al. (2021), and this unidimensional scale comprises eight items. The Cronbach's alpha for AMSS was 0.862.
4. Behavioral Intention to Attend University Events Scale (BIAUES) developed by Harb et al. (2021), this unidimensional scale initially had three items, with an additional two items incorporated for this study. It has a total of five items. The Cronbach's alpha for BIAUES was 0.868.

After securing approval from the relevant offices, the researchers collected the data through face-to-face engagement with the respondents from July 8, 2024, to July 24, 2024. The researchers informed the respondents about the aims of the study, and written informed consent was obtained. The identity of the respondents was anonymous, and they were not offered incentives. Moreover, they briefed the respondents on the study's objectives, their rights, and the confidentiality of their responses. The study was approved and conducted following the recommendations of the Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics Committee.

For the data analysis, the researchers used descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic factors related to the respondents'

schools or colleges. The mean and standard deviation for all scales were calculated, and the relationships among the study's variables were explored using bivariate correlations. Then, they investigated the influence of classroom cultural diversity climate on the intention to engage in cultural events, mediated by attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence, using parallel mediation analysis using JASP 0.19.0.

Results

Table 1 displays the level of classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, and the intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of The Variable of the Study

Variable and Factors	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
1. Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	3.39	0.419	Very High
1.1. Contact and Cooperation	3.48	0.738	Very High
1.2. Equal Treatment	3.44	0.492	Very High
1.3. Color Inclusivity	3.50	0.497	Very High
1.4. Heritage, Culture, and Intercultural Learning	3.30	0.491	Very High
1.5. Critical Consciousness	3.26	0.512	Very High
1.6. Polyculturalism	3.36	0.487	Very High
2. Attitude to Multiculturalism at School	3.57	0.511	Very High
3. Cultural Competence	3.14	0.382	High
3.1. Knowledge	3.08	0.448	High
3.2. Awareness of Others	3.30	0.430	High
3.3. Proactive Skills Development	2.98	0.502	High
3.4. Awareness of Self	3.21	0.559	High
4. Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	3.33	0.574	Very High

The classroom cultural diversity climate had a very high rating ($M = 3.39$, $SD = 0.419$). This indicates a strong and consistent positive perception among the Holy Cross of Davao College students. All factors under classroom cultural diversity consistently, got a very high descriptive level. Breaking this down, the factor color inclusivity obtained the highest mean score ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 0.497$), followed by contact and cooperation ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 0.738$), equal treatment ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.492$), polyculturalism ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.487$), heritage, culture, and intercultural learning ($M = 3.30$, $SD = 0.491$), and lastly, critical consciousness ($M = 3.26$, $SD = 0.512$).

Moreover, the second variable involved in this study, the attitude to multiculturalism in school got a very high rating ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.511$), reflecting a positive and consistent attitude towards multiculturalism among Holy Cross of Davao College students. Furthermore, the third variable in this study, cultural competence, got a

very high rating ($M = 3.14$, $SD = 0.382$). Within this variable, four factors obtained high descriptive level, and the factor that obtained the highest mean is awareness of others ($M = 3.30$, $SD = 0.430$), followed by awareness of self ($M = 3.21$, $SD = 0.559$), knowledge ($M = 3.08$, $SD = 0.448$), and lastly, proactive skills development ($M = 2.98$, $SD = 0.502$). Finally, the intention to engage in cultural events had a rating of very high ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 0.574$), indicating a strong and consistent intention among students to participate in organized cultural activities and will continuously be organized by the Holy Cross of Davao College – Center for Culture and the Arts.

Moreover, Table 2 displays the correlation manifested among Holy Cross of Davao College students' perceived classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism at school, cultural competence, and their intention to engage in cultural events.

Table 2. Bivariate Correlations Among Study Variables

Variables	r	Interpretation	H ₀ 1 Decision
CCDC and AtMS	.586**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject
CCDC and CIC	.589**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject
CCDC and ItEiCE	.417**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject
AtMS and CIC	.454**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject
AtMS and ItEiCE	.453**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject
CC and AtMS	.492**	Moderate Correlation	Fail to Reject

Note: Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate (CCDC), Attitude to Multiculturalism at School (AtMS), Cultural Competence (CIC), Intention to Engage in Cultural Events (ItEiCE), and **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Pearson correlations were estimated among the study variables. Classroom cultural diversity climate was positively correlated with attitude to multiculturalism in school ($r = .586$, p -value < 0.01), cultural competence ($r = .589$, p -value < 0.01), and intention to engage in cultural events ($r = .417$, p -value < 0.01). Additionally, the attitude to multiculturalism in school was positively correlated with cultural competence ($r = .454$, p -value < 0.01) and the intention to engage in cultural events ($r = .453$, p -value < 0.01). Lastly, cultural competence was positively correlated with the intention to engage in cultural events ($r = .492$, p -value < 0.01). Collectively, from the observed significant

positive correlations, the decision for H₀1 is to fail to reject.

Lastly, Table 3 displays parallel mediation analysis having the attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence as the two mediating variables that potentially mediate the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events among the Holy Cross of Davao College students or simply the path coefficients for the multi-mediator model. Moreover, the standardized effects will be featured in Table 4. Furthermore, the multi-mediator model is shown in Figure 1.

Table 3. Path Coefficients for the Mediation Model

							95% Confidence Interval	
			Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	Lower	Upper
Attitude to Multiculturalism at School	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.263	0.039	6.728	< .001	0.174	0.392
Cultural Competence	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.334	0.039	8.516	< .001	0.239	0.421
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.156	0.103	1.517	0.129	-0.075	0.384
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Attitude to Multiculturalism at School	1.398	0.073	19.218	< .001	1.130	1.601
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Cultural Competence	1.404	0.073	19.345	< .001	1.194	1.617

Table 4. Parameter Estimates

			Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Direct Effects								
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.156	0.103	1.517	0.129	-0.074	0.392
Indirect Effects								
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Attitude to Multiculturalism at School	0.368	0.058	6.350	<.001	0.224	0.576
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Cultural Competence	0.469	0.060	7.794	<.001	0.333	0.627
Total Effects								
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.993	0.082	12.164	<.001	0.810	1.164
Total Indirect Effects								
Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate	→	Intention to Engage in Cultural Events	0.837	0.078	10.689	<.001	0.625	1.069
Residual Covariances								
Attitude to Multiculturalism at School	↔	Cultural Competence	0.109	0.025	4.357	<.001	0.057	0.176

Note: Number of bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals: 5,000 and R²: Intention to Engage in Cultural Events = 0.311; Attitude to Multiculturalism at School = 0.344; Cultural Competence = 0.347

A parallel mediation analysis was performed with a bootstrapping resampling procedure to examine the indirect effect of classroom cultural diversity climate on the intention of the college students to engage in institutional cultural events through attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence. The results showed that classroom cultural diversity climate was a significant predictor of attitude to multiculturalism in school ($\beta = 1.398, p < 0.001$) and cultural competence ($\beta = 1.404, p < 0.001$). On the contrary, the direct effect revealed that classroom cultural diversity climate was not a significant predictor of intention to engage in institutional cultural events ($\beta = 0.156, p 0.129$). Classroom cultural diversity climate explained 34.4% of the variance in attitude to multiculturalism in school and 34.7% of the variance in cultural competence.

Additionally, the results indicated that classroom cultural diversity climate had indirect effects on intention to engage in institutional cultural events through attitude to multiculturalism in school ($\beta = 0.368, p < 0.001$) and cultural competence ($\beta = 0.469, p < 0.001$). Attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence fully mediated the effect of classroom cultural diversity climate on intention to engage in institutional cultural events. Hence, the decision for H_02 is to fail to reject. Classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude to multiculturalism in school, and cultural competence collectively accounted for 31.1% of the variance in intention to engage in institutional cultural events. The indirect effects of classroom cultural diversity climate on intention to engage in institutional cultural events through attitude to multiculturalism in school and cultural competence was significant.

Figure 2. Path Plot Model of Classroom Cultural Diversity Climate (CCDC) and Intention to Engage in Cultural Events (ItEiCE) with Parallel Mediators Attitude to Multiculturality at School (AtMaS) and Cultural Competence (CIC)

Considering the findings, it is evident that focusing solely on the perceived classroom cultural diversity climate of the college students is insufficient; their attitude toward multiculturalism and cultural competence at Holy Cross of Davao College must also be addressed, as these factors significantly influence their intention to engage in cultural events. To address this, an institutional culture-based activity titled *Panagsandug*, a *Mandaya* term meaning "solidarity," will be its guiding principle, for this underscores the need for unity and collective appreciation of the diverse culture and heritage of Davao. *Panagsandug* will be spearheaded by the Holy Cross of Davao College-Center for Culture and the Arts, aiming to sustain and further intensify the classroom cultural diversity climate, attitude toward multiculturalism, and cultural competence of the students. This initiative will

involve collaboration with the academic stakeholders, particularly the teaching staff of the institution, and will guarantee a comprehensive and inclusive approach to cultural education and engagement.

Collectively, *Panagsandug* culture and the arts program aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals—particularly Goal 4: Quality Education, Goal 5: Gender Equality, and Goal 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions. This cultural education initiative aspires to cultivate a sense of cultural appreciation, inclusivity, and unity, which are vital for building a peaceful and just society.

Discussion

Holy Cross of Davao College students perceived their classroom environment as highly diverse and inclusive. This finding revealed that students were able to experience increased cultural sensitivity, enhanced cultural diversity learning opportunities, better preparation for the future, and the development of meaningful intercultural relationships among their classmates and teachers. This result agrees with prior studies revealing that students recognize and value cultural diversity in their classrooms, which contributes further to positive and meaningful educational outcomes (Jeannin, 2013; Grover et al., 2020). Moreover, students hold positive views regarding multiculturalism at Holy Cross of Davao College. This suggests that students hold positive views regarding multiculturalism in the school environment, which can foster greater social and school integration and create a more inclusive and harmonious school climate. This result aligns with findings from other studies, such as those conducted in cities in the Central Anatolia and Marmara regions, and among Croatian and Serbian respondents in Vukovar, where students also exhibited positive attitudes towards multiculturalism (Köşker & Özgen, 2018; Ćorkalo Biruški & Ajduković, 2012, as cited by Mičić, 2018).

On the other hand, students possess a high level of cultural competence in the aspects of knowledge, awareness of others, proactive skills development, and self-awareness regarding cultural diversity. High cultural competence among Holy Cross of Davao College students suggests that they are prepared to interact with diverse populations in the community and can contribute positively to a multicultural society. These findings align with previous research studies where undergraduate students reported high levels of self-perceived cultural competence, highlighting the significance of cultural competency in fostering better citizenship (Erba et al., 2020; Cuyjet, 2020). Furthermore, the intention of the Holy Cross of Davao College students to engage in institutional cultural events is very high. Such engagement also suggests that students recognize the value of cultural events in enhancing their educational

experience and personal growth. This result agrees with earlier studies where students showed intention to engage in cultural events, which was manifested in their active participation in social and cultural activities, emphasizing the significance of cultural representation on campus (Hendricks, 2023; Kus, 2015; Specht, 2020).

Beyond the observed significant correlations to all the variables in this study, the interesting result obtained is that attitudes towards multiculturalism in school and cultural competence fully mediated the relationship between classroom cultural diversity climate and the intention to engage in cultural events. A positive diversity climate alone is insufficient; the attitudes and competence of the students significantly influence their engagement in school cultural events. This finding highlights the critical role of a supportive classroom environment in shaping the attitudes and competencies of students, which drive their engagement. Previous research supports this notion, indicating that a positive classroom environment predicts the attitudes of the students toward school, enhances their learning experiences, develops competency, and fosters engagement in school activities (Nazneen et al., 2019; Marangell et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2022; Allen et al., 2018; Dang & Nguyen, 2021; Kacane, 2021).

Lastly, on closely examining the theoretical perspective, Bandura's social cognitive theory asserts that behavior is affected by the interaction between personal factors, environmental influences, and behaviors. The positive classroom cultural diversity climate is an environmental influence that shapes students' attitudes (personal factors) and competencies, driving their engagement in cultural events (behavior). This reciprocal interaction aligns with SCT's core principles, suggesting that the supportive and diverse classroom environment at Holy Cross of Davao College plays a crucial role in fostering positive attitudes and cultural competencies, thereby promoting students' active participation in cultural events. Thus, the study's results strongly support and affirm Bandura's social cognitive theory.

Summary of Findings

1. Classroom cultural diversity climate got a very high rating as perceived by the students. This means that the classroom environment at Holy Cross of Davao College is highly diverse and actively promotes intercultural learning and inclusivity.
2. Students' attitudes toward multiculturalism at school got a very high rating. These students actively support and value multicultural perspectives as essential to the school experience.
3. Students' cultural competence got a high rating. This means they are generally competent in interacting with people from diverse cultural backgrounds and have essential cultural knowledge and awareness.
4. Students' intention to engage in cultural events got a very high rating. This means they actively seek out and would like to regularly participate in cultural events and activities in school.
5. Attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence were influential mediating variables in the association between classroom cultural diversity climate and students' intention to engage in cultural events.

Conclusion

The study findings reveal that Holy Cross of Davao College students perceive the classroom cultural diversity climate and their attitude towards multiculturalism at school to be very high, with cultural competence also rated high and a very high intention to engage in cultural events. A significant moderate positive correlation exists among these variables, indicating that as one increases, so do the others, which led to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis one (H_01). Furthermore, the analysis shows that attitude to multiculturalism at school and cultural competence fully mediate the relationship between the classroom cultural diversity climate and intention to engage in cultural events, leading to a decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis two (H_02).

To increase the intention of college students' engagement in cultural events and activities in school, focusing on improving their attitudes towards multiculturalism and enhancing cultural competence may be more effective than directly giving due attention to the classroom diversity climate alone. With this, the Holy Cross of Davao College - Center for Culture and the Arts and Institute of Davao Studies will consider implementing a cultural education symposium that will focus on promoting positive attitudes towards multiculturalism and building cultural competence, as these factors are crucial in driving students' engagement in cultural events. Moreover, teachers and other academic stakeholders will also be part of this symposium as they are known to be the curriculum designers and implementers.

Further, the study depended on self-reported measures, which could present response biases. Hence, future research should incorporate a broader range of institutions and employ mixed methods to capture a thorough understanding of cultural dynamics in an educational environment. Scholars must persist in conducting research that addresses the pressing needs of society. With this, scholars need to continue exploring cultural studies within the academic context to develop more effective strategies for cultivating cultural competence, promoting multicultural attitudes, and enriching engagement in cultural activities among students. These steps are vital in building inclusive and culturally rich educational environments that prepare students to thrive in a diverse and interconnected world.

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Ethics Statement

The researchers adhere to the mandate of the Department of Science of Technology-Philippine Health Research Ethics Board on universal ethical principles of respecting the rights of the respondents and aligned with the observance of ethical considerations in research per CMO 15, s.2019. With this, the study was subjected to an ethical assessment by the Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics

Committee and was given clearance to gather data dated July 8, 2024. In the conduct of the study, the researchers adhere to the nine ethical principles set forth by the committee which are, social value, informed consent, risk, benefits, and safety, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

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Conflict of Interests

The researchers declared that there was no emerging conflict of interest in the conduct of the study.

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